

**LEVELS OF TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION
IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
SIAYA, KISUMU AND KAJIADO COUNTIES, KENYA**

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Abstract:

Teachers' job satisfaction is one of the fundamental factors that determine the success of any school. A satisfied teacher would most likely put in more effort towards the success of a school while a dissatisfied teacher would lazy around and students would not reap the full benefits of education. This study examined the levels of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties, Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey paradigm. The study was guided by the Herzberg's Two Factor Theory. The target population comprised of 379 deputy principals, 1010 heads of departments, and 2208 teachers in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties, Kenya who had served for more than two years in the same school. Stratified and simple random sampling was used to sample 38 deputy principals, 101 heads of departments and 221 teachers giving a total of 360 respondents. The data for this study was collected using Teacher Job Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found out that most (56.7%) teachers were dissatisfied and that most (63.9%) of them would not choose teaching as a profession if they were to start over again in a new career. The study concluded that a dissatisfied teaching force is disastrous for the education sector in Kenya as this will prevent learners from reaping the full benefits of education. The study recommends that education stakeholders and policy makers should put in place

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appropriate mechanisms that will address the challenges around the attainment of teachers' job satisfaction in Kenya.

Keywords: job satisfaction, teaching profession, intrinsic factors, extrinsic factors

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction plays an important role in maintaining the quality of human resources in any organization. It is known to greatly impact on employees' performance. It has a great relationship with employees work performance and organizational productivity. According to Ombemi (2016), job satisfaction is one of the cornerstones of a healthier secondary school. This is because a contented teacher would most likely put in more effort towards the success of a school. On the contrary, a dissatisfied teacher would lazy around and students will not reap the full benefits of education (World Bank, 2015). The happier people are with their job, the more satisfied they are which results to higher productivity, morale and initiative (Furnham, 1997). This finding is in line with Roethlisberger (1949) earlier study which noted that unsatisfied workers are less productive.

De Nobile and McCormick (2006) noted that low levels of satisfaction are linked to negative behavior, lower commitment and lower productivity. They further noted that teachers who experienced low job satisfaction suffered from psychological withdrawal from the job, poor interpersonal relationship with staff, students and administration and absenteeism resulting to students' poor performance. Schools need satisfied and motivated teachers who can work efficiently and effectively with undue supervision for the attainment of school goals and productivity (Timothy et.al, 2001). A study conducted by World Bank (2015) reported that when teachers are supported and celebrated for their achievements, then their job satisfaction is raised. This will enhance students' achievement. Therefore, any challenges around the attainment of teachers' job satisfaction can demise the attainment of school goals.

Various studies across the globe have shockingly revealed a very low level of teacher job satisfaction. In a UNESCO's study conducted across the globe, only 8.6% of the teachers were satisfied while 58.1% wanted to quit teaching (World Bank, 2015). In South Africa, the National Professional Teachers Organization of South Africa's (NAPTOS) report indicated that 32.8% of the teachers had a negative morale towards teaching (NAPTOS, 2013). The study further noted that poor leadership style contributed immensely (65.5%) to teacher job dissatisfaction. A similar study by Anguyo (2014) in Uganda indicated that 47% of the teachers were dissatisfied.

In Kenya, the problem of teacher job dissatisfaction dates back to the pre-colonial period (Bogonko, 1994). The professional life expectancy of the members of the teaching profession was relatively low. More was heard of teacher professionals exodus to other jobs than one heard among other professions (Gachathi, 1976). According to a recent survey by Education International, which was reported by Oduor (2015), half of the Kenyan teachers want other jobs while 45% would like to quit teaching. This implies that of the 300,000 Kenyan teachers, 135,000 would wish to quit the teaching profession. Factors contributing to low teacher job satisfaction in Kenya, according to the survey, were poor working conditions, poor leadership style, and lack of recognition of teachers by the public, lack of promotion, heavy workload, poor school policies, supervision and poor human relations.

Due to its relevance to the physical and mental wellbeing of the teachers, and its implication on employee activity, teachers' job satisfaction has been widely researched. However, most researchers (Herzberg 1959; Wu and Short, 1996) put more emphasis on intrinsic factors while others (Dvorack and Philips, 2001, Education International, 2015) focused on extrinsic factors. In order to manage this study the researcher used the mixed approach and studied both intrinsic and extrinsic factors of job satisfaction. Furthermore, none of the studies establishes to what extent the teachers are dissatisfied and in which aspects particularly in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the levels of teacher job satisfaction in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

(i) The study was guided by the objective: to find out levels of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties.

1.4 Research Question

(i) What is the level of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties?

1.5 Significance of the Study

There is a general perception that teachers in Kenya are dissatisfied with their profession. However, there is no recent study that establishes to what extent the teachers are dissatisfied and in which aspects particularly in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties. The findings of this study would shed light into these aspects and would

help policy makers, ministry of education and Teachers' Service Commission to put in place appropriate measures that would entice teachers to like their job.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Review of related literature focused on the concept job satisfaction, teacher job satisfaction and levels of teacher job satisfaction in Kenya.

2.2 The Concept Job Satisfaction

The concept job satisfaction has been defined in many different ways by different scholars. According to Nguni et al (2006), job satisfaction is a pleasurable emotional state resulting from an individual's view of the job as achieving one's personal values. It is the overall feeling about one's career in terms of specifics such as compensation, autonomy, recognition, co-worker and administration (Luthans, 1994; Wetherel, 2002). Jayaratne (1993) observed that job satisfaction is an assessment of one's job as fulfilling one's important values and needs. It is the degree to which one loves his/her job. The happier a person is with his or her job the more satisfied and productive one is (Furnham, 1997). It follows therefore that, workers who are satisfied are more productive compared to unsatisfied ones. Hukpati (2009) on the hand defined job satisfaction as an employee's attitudes about the job and job conditions. He postulated that job satisfaction leads to a general feeling of fulfillment and positive work attitudes to the worker. Job satisfaction therefore enables the worker to be innovative, focused and committed to the organization's mission and vision.

2.3 Teacher Job Satisfaction

Teacher job satisfaction basically refers to the teacher's overall feeling about the teaching profession in terms of what teaching offers and what the teacher wants from teaching. It is the degree to which a teacher loves his teaching profession. Job satisfaction of teachers can be measured against productivity since it has great impact on students learning. According to Choy (1993), dissatisfied teachers are less motivated to perform their duties while those who are satisfied effectively do their work and are likely to remain in the teaching profession or in the same school. Herzberg et al., (1959) supported the above view and noted that positive feelings about one's job and a sense of personal recognition and fulfillment were related to achievement and productivity.

Educational scholars such Davis (1992) and Johnson (2003) noted that low levels of teacher job satisfaction are linked to negative behaviors such as psychological

withdrawal from the job, lower commitment, lower productivity, poor staff interrelations, absenteeism and high staff turn-over. Considering the above stated adverse effects, raising the levels of teacher job satisfaction becomes paramount. It can be concluded that when teachers are supported, valued and recognized for their achievements, satisfaction levels, work productivity and performance are increased. Lumsden (1998) in his study on teacher job satisfaction reported that teachers identified administrative support, leadership styles, teacher autonomy and a positive school environment as some of the factors related to teacher job satisfaction. De Nobile and McCormick (2008b) found out in their study that levels of job satisfaction felt by teachers in similar work environment can vary from one individual to the other. This was due to the fact that a variety of factors and dimensions can influence a persons' level of satisfaction.

According to Herzberg's "two factor" Motivation-Hygiene theory, employee's satisfaction is a multifaceted construct driven by two sets of factors known as motivation factors and the hygiene factors. The motivation factors apply to the intrinsic aspects of a teachers' work that make them want to perform and include teachers' feelings of successful outcomes (achievement), recognition, responsibility (teacher autonomy), opportunity for advancement (professional growth) and the work itself (the intellectual challenge of teaching), (Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman, 1959; Herzberg, 1968; Hackman and Oldham, 1976). Since these factors arise from the work itself, they are called intrinsic and relate with higher levels of satisfaction. Their presence enhances teacher job satisfaction (Noddings, 2006; Houtte, 2006).

The hygiene factors (dissatisfies) on the hand operate to reduce or eliminate job dissatisfaction. These factors correspond to the extrinsic aspects of teaching and are related to lower levels of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. They are factors pertinent to a teachers' working environment and include working conditions, work overload, supervision (strong leadership), pay, work policy, job status (perceptions on how the society view teachers), interpersonal relationships with co-workers and children, desire to improve children's lives and administrative support (Herzberg et al., 1959).

Generally, the motivators attract people to join the teaching profession while the hygiene factors determine their level of satisfaction and the desire to remain in the teaching profession (Azar & Henden, 2003; Papanastasiou & Zemblas, 2006). Absence of hygiene factors can cause great frustration leading to dissatisfaction (Katie, 2013). According to Blanford (2000), satisfied teachers perform better. This has a direct influence on the academic success, emotional, social, and cognitive development of the children. It is therefore important to observe that principals should ensure a high level of teacher job satisfaction since it has a positive impact on the quality of teaching.

2.4 Levels of Teacher Job Satisfaction in Kenya

Various studies across the globe have shockingly revealed a very low level of teacher job satisfaction. This is very unfortunate since teachers' job satisfaction has a remarkable effect on students' performance. In a UNESCO study conducted across the globe, half of the teachers were somewhat dissatisfied while 18.2% were very dissatisfied (World Bank, 2015). A study by US Department of Education (1993) noted that 40% of USA teachers were strongly dissatisfied. In Bangladesh, Tasnim (2006) found that both female and male teachers were dissatisfied. Similar results were reported by Anguyo (2014) in Uganda where he noted that only 16% of the Ugandan primary school teachers aspire to remain in the teaching profession while 49% of the teaching force was very dissatisfied. A study by Adeyami (2014) in Nigeria noted moderate teacher job satisfaction.

In Kenya, since the pre-colonial period, the professional life expectancy of the teaching profession has been relatively low (Bogonko, 1994). As a result, the country has experienced high teacher turn-over over the years. The Kenya Secondary Schools Heads Association (KSSHA) 2008 estimates showed that at least 600 teachers quit the profession yearly for other jobs (Omwoyo, 2014). In 2016 alone 2,157 teachers exited the profession (Oduor, 2017).

The Education and Health Services in Kenya – Data for Results and Accountability Report cited chronic absenteeism as one of the problems of teacher job dissatisfaction in Kenya. The report indicated that in a fifth of the schools surveyed, teacher absence rate was between 20% and 40%. The report further noted that for every 100 public school teachers, 27 were present in school but not teaching (Kamuri, 2014). In another study by Education International, 45% of the teachers wanted to quit teaching while only 55% of the 300,000 Kenyan teachers were ready to retire in the profession. This explains why there has been a series of industrial actions by teachers in the recent past which has seen education in public institutions ground to a halt as teachers demanded improvement in their working conditions (Oduor, 2015).

This low level of teacher job satisfaction is disastrous to the Kenya education system. According to Mwamwenda (1995), lack of job satisfaction has implications for the teacher as well as the education system. This is because teacher job satisfaction determines their morale and the amount of effort they put towards maximizing their teaching potential. Teacher job dissatisfaction results in bad teaching which will consequently affect students learning.

In conclusion, the reviewed literature indicates a general perception that most teachers in Kenya are dissatisfied (Okubmbe, 1994; Kamuri, 2014; Oduor, 2015; Oduor, 2017). However, there is no recent study that establishes to what extent the teachers are

dissatisfied or satisfied and in which aspects particularly in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties, Kenya. This study intended to fill this gap.

3. Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design to examine the levels of teacher job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties. According to Kothari (2003), descriptive survey is a method of securing information concerning an existing phenomenon from all or a selected number of respondents of a concerned universe. Survey was used because there was a systematic collection of data from members of a given population through questionnaires (Orodho, 2005) which in this case were deputy principals, heads of departments and teachers.

3.2 Target Population

The target population comprised of 379 deputy principals, 1010 heads of departments and 2208 secondary school teachers in the respective counties who had served for at least two years in the same school giving a total of 3615 respondents.

3.3 Sample Size

Stratified and simple random sampling was used to select 38 deputy principals, 101 heads of departments and 221 secondary school teachers giving a total of 360 respondents.

3.4 Research Instruments

The study employed Teacher Job Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire which was used to seek information from various sample groups and the data obtained were subjected to descriptive techniques. Questionnaires were used to collect data from deputy principals, heads of departments and teachers to gather quantitative data on the levels of teacher job satisfaction in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties as perceived by teachers.

3.5 Piloting Reliability

A pilot study was carried out on three deputy principals, three heads of departments and six secondary school teachers from three different schools to establish the reliability of the research instruments through a test-retest.

3.6 Validity

To validate the research instruments, expert opinion from my supervisors and other experts from Kenyatta University was sought to help check on the content and construct validity of the instruments. They read through the draft instruments and thereafter their recommendations were incorporated in the coming up with the final instruments that were used in the study.

3.7 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data. Results were analyzed using simple and inferential statistics in the form of frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviations, one way analysis of variance and chi-square.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Levels of Teacher Job Satisfaction with the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Dimension of Job Satisfaction

Using 4 as the mid-point, Table 4.1 show that most (70.1%) teachers were satisfied with the extrinsic dimension of job satisfaction compared to intrinsic dimension (27.2%) of job satisfaction.

Table 4.1: Levels of Teachers' Job Satisfaction with Intrinsic/Extrinsic Dimensions of Job Satisfaction (n = 231)

Job satisfaction Dimension	Teacher Category	Job Satisfaction Levels										Total	
		1		2		3		4		5		n	%
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Intrinsic													
	D/principals	2	5.7	19	54.3	14	40	0	0.0	0	0.0	35	100
	H.O.Ds	0	0.0	19	24.4	27	34.6	29	37.0	3	3.8	78	100
	Teachers	8	6.8	30	25.4	49	41.5	21	18.0	10	8.5	118	100
	Total	10	4.3	68	29.5	90	39.0	50	21.6	13	5.6	231	100
Extrinsic													
	D/principals	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	17.1	26	74	3	8.6	35	100
	H.O.Ds	0	0.0	3	3.8	28	35.9	46	59	1	1.3	78	100
	Teachers	0	0.0	2	1.7	30	25.4	71	60	15	12.7	118	100
	Total	0	0.0	5	2.2	64	27.7	143	61.9	19	8.2	231	100

1-very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

The above findings reflect the views of Azar and Henden (2003), and Papanastasiou and Zemblas, (2006) who noted that motivators (intrinsic factors) attract people to join the

teaching profession while hygiene (extrinsic) factors determine their level of satisfaction and the desire to remain in the teaching profession.

Results in Table 4.2 further indicated that responsibility (M=3.74. SD, 0.938) was the highest intrinsic contributing factor of teacher job satisfaction while potential for advancement (M= 3.27.SD, 1.054) was the least intrinsic contributing factor of job satisfaction.

Table 4.2: Mean Response Scores for Intrinsic Job Satisfaction Factors

Job Satisfaction Measures	Mean	Std. Deviation
Responsibility	3.74	0.938
Achievement	3.59	0.900
Professional Growth	3.58	0.979
Recognition	3.57	0.887
Advancement	3.27	1.054

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

Among the extrinsic factors of job satisfaction, the study established that interpersonal relationships with students (M= 4.11. SD, 0.720) was the highest perceived contributing factor of teacher job satisfaction followed by sense of accountability (M= 4.05. SD, 0.31) and supervision (M = 3.92. SD, 0.787). Salary scored the lowest (M= 2.22. SD, 1.09) indicating that teachers were somewhat dissatisfied with the salary they are earning as shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Mean Response Scores for Extrinsic Job Satisfaction Factors

Job Satisfaction Measures	Mean	Std. Deviation
Interpersonal relationship with students	4.11	0.720
Sense of accountability	4.05	0.731
Supervision	3.92	0.787
Interpersonal relationship with administrators	3.75	0.888
Teacher evaluation	3.73	0.844
School policies	3.71	0.910
The profession itself	3.37	1.045
Status	3.34	1.082
Working conditions	2.27	1.127
Salary	2.22	1.090

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

In summary, participants were satisfied with the job factors interpersonal relationships with students (M= 4.11. SD, 0.720) and sense of accountability (M= 4.05. SD, 0.731). They

felt somewhat dissatisfied with their salaries (M= 2.22. SD, 1.092) which they perceived to be low compared to others with similar qualifications in other organizations. This finding was consistent with Okumbe (1992) who noted that a poor salary was a major concern for the teaching profession in Kenya since independence. It should be noted with great concern that this equitable underpay which teachers perceive in the job is a more decisive determinant of dissatisfaction than an equitable pay would determine their satisfaction level.

4.2 Opportunity to Choose Teaching as a Profession

Findings from the analysis of teachers' job satisfaction with intrinsic and extrinsic dimensions of satisfaction were further corroborated by findings of their level of satisfaction with choosing teaching as a profession if they were to start over again in a new carrier. Point 4 in the scale was used as the mid-point between satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Results are shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Opportunity to Choose Teaching as a Profession (n = 231)

Teacher Category	Job Satisfaction											
	1		2		3		4		5		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%
D/Principals	8	22.9	4	11.4	8	22.9	8	22.8	7	20.0	35	100
HODS	21	26.9	18	23.1	21	26.8	13	16.7	5	6.5	78	100
Teachers	28	23.8	10	8.4	30	25.4	29	24.6	21	17.8	118	100
Total	57	24.7	32	13.8	59	25.4	50	21.5	34	14.6	231	100

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5-very satisfied

When asked to rate themselves on satisfaction with choosing teaching as a career if they were given the opportunity to start over again, a paltry 14.6% of the respondents were very satisfied while only 21.5% were satisfied with choosing the teaching profession as a career. The implication about this is that most (63.9%) respondents would not choose teaching again as a profession. This finding is in line with the findings by Omwoyo (2014) who noted that at least 800 teachers quit the profession yearly for other jobs in Kenya. In another study by Education International (2014), 45% of teachers in Kenya would want to quit teaching while only about 55% would want to retire in teaching.

4.3 Overall Satisfaction with Teaching as a Profession

Teachers were finally to rate their overall level of satisfaction with the teaching profession. Results are shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Level of Satisfaction with the Teaching Profession (n = 231)

Teacher Category	Job Satisfaction											
	1		2		3		4		5		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
D/Principals	1	2.9	5	14.3	10	28.6	13	37.1	6	17.1	35	100
HODS	10	12.8	14	18.0	26	33.3	22	28.2	6	7.7	78	100
Teachers	14	8.4	21	16.8	30	28.0	33	28.0	20	18.7	118	100
Total	25	10.8	40	17.3	66	28.6	68	29.4	32	13.9	231	100

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5-very satisfied

Concerning the general level of satisfaction with teaching as a profession, paltry (13.9%) teachers were very satisfied while only (29.4%) stated that they were satisfied. The implication about this finding is that most (56.7%) teachers were dissatisfied with the teaching profession. This finding supports the findings in the background study where a UNESCO study across the globe established that half the teachers were somewhat dissatisfied (World Bank, 2015). In a similar study in Uganda, Anguyo (2014) found out that 49% of the teachers were very dissatisfied.

The above findings are disastrous to the education system in Kenya since teacher job satisfaction determines their morale and the amount of effort they put towards maximizing their teaching potential.

4.5 Effects of General and Demographic Variables on Perceived Teacher Job Satisfaction

It was important to determine whether patterns emerged between job satisfaction and category variables such as school type, gender, teaching experience, level of education, length of time teaching in same school, length of time worked with a principal and grade level. Chi squares were therefore calculated to determine whether or not patterns emerged between perceived job satisfaction and the category variables. Results are shown in Tables 4.6, 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9.

Table 4.6: Job Satisfaction and Type of School

Type of school	Job Satisfaction										Total	
	1		2		3		4		5			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Girls boarding	1	1.9	4	7.5	19	35.8	20	37.7	9	17.0	53	100
Boys boarding	0	0.0	6	8.1	26	35.1	34	45.9	8	10.8	74	100
Mixed	0	0.0	14	9.8	60	42.0	57	39.9	12	8.4	143	100
χ^2	Statistic		8.402									
	df		8									
	Sig		0.395									

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

Chi square results in Table 4.6 indicate that type of school the teacher serves in had no significant influence on job satisfaction ($\chi^2(8) = 8.402, p > .05$).

Table 4.7: Job Satisfaction and Gender

Gender	Job satisfaction										Total	
	1		2		3		4		5			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Male	0	0.0	12	7.7	61	39.1	66	42.3	17	10.9	156	100
Female	1	0.9	12	10.5	44	38.6	45	39.5	12	10.5	114	100
χ^2	Statistic		2.105									
	df		4									
	Sig		0.716									

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

Out of the 270 teachers who participated in the study, 156 were males and 114 were females. Chi square results in Table 4.31 indicated that job satisfaction was independent of gender ($\chi^2(4) = 2.105, p > .05$). Any significant effect on Job satisfaction could therefore be as a result of leadership style and not gender.

Table 4.8: Job Satisfaction and Teaching Experience

Years	Job Satisfaction										Total	
	1		2		3		4		5			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
2-7	1	1.2	7	8.6	27	33.3	34	42.0	12	14.8	81	100
8-12	0	0.0	4	8.5	20	42.6	18	38.3	5	10.6	47	100
13-18	0	0.0	9	14.8	23	37.7	26	42.6	3	4.9	61	100
19 and above	0	0.0	4	4.9	35	43.2	33	40.7	9	11.1	81	100
χ^2	Statistic			10.68								
	df			12								
	Sig			0.557								

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

Chi square results in Table 4.8 shows that job satisfaction was independent of teaching experience ($\chi^2(12) = 10.675, p > .05$).

Table 4.9: Job Satisfaction and Level of Education

Level of Education	Job Satisfaction										Total	
	1		2		3		4		5			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Diploma	0	0.0	3	5.8	19	36.5	22	42.3	8	15.4	52	100
Graduate	1	0.7	17	11.3	54	36.0	66	44.0	12	8.0	150	100
Masters	0	0.0	4	6.3	28	44.4	22	39.0	9	14.3	63	100
PhD	0	0.4	0	8.9	4	38.9	1	41.1	0	10.7	5	100
χ^2	Statistic			11.167								
	df			12								
	Sig			0.515								

1- very dissatisfied; 2- somewhat dissatisfied; 3- somewhat satisfied; 4- satisfied; 5- very satisfied

Chi square results in Table 4.9 also indicate that job satisfaction was independent of level of education ($\chi^2(12) = 11.167, p > .05$). The influence of teachers' level of education was therefore negligible and thus controlled for.

In summary, these results indicated that variables such as school type, gender, teaching experience, number of years served with the principal and teachers' level of education had no significant influence on perceived teacher job satisfaction.

5. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the levels of teachers' job satisfaction in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado Counties in Kenya. The study was guided by the following objective; to find out the levels of teachers' job satisfaction in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado Counties in Kenya

The study established that most (56.7%) teachers were dissatisfied with their job and that most (63.9%) of them would not choose the teaching profession if they were to start over again in a new carrier. They however exuded more (70.1%) satisfaction with extrinsic factors compared to intrinsic factors of job satisfaction (27.2%). The main contributing factors to job satisfaction among intrinsic factors were responsibility ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.938$) and achievement ($M = 3.59$, $SD = 0.900$). Among the extrinsic factors, interpersonal relationship with students ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.720$), accountability ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.731$) and supervision ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.787$) were the main contributing factors to teacher job satisfaction. Salary had the least score ($M = 2.22$, $SD = 1.090$) indicating that teachers perceived salary as dissatisfying and low compared to others with similar qualifications in other organizations. No association was found between teachers' level of satisfaction and variables such as school type, gender, teaching experience, number of years served with the principal, grade level and teachers' level of education.

5.2 Conclusions

This study concluded that the fact that most teachers were dissatisfied and would not choose the teaching profession again if they were to start over again in a new career is disastrous for the education sector in Kenya.

5.3 Recommendations

The study recommended that;

- i. Principals, consultants and other education stakeholders need to design programs that will help create greater collegiality, sense of mission and team building opportunities with staff. This will entice teachers to like their job and therefore remain committed and focused.
- ii. The Ministry of Education should endeavor to develop and improve on existing leadership policies, practices and frameworks that would help address the challenges facing the teaching profession in Kenya.

5.4 Recommendations for Further Research

The research sought to find out the levels of teachers' job satisfaction in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado counties, Kenya. The researcher suggests other studies as follows:

- i. A study of the same nature should be replicated in other counties in Kenya for purposes of comparison and generalization.
- ii. In terms of wider application, future studies should be conducted in higher educational institutions such as universities and colleges.

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